

ANIQ FANLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AYOLLARNING ROLI: GENDER TENGLIGI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14981590>

Annotatsiya. Malakali kadrlar yetishmovchiligi innovatsion faoliyatga to'sqinlik qiluvchi, mehnat unumdorligini o'sishi va iqtisodiyot rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qiluvchi asosiy omillardan biridir. Xususan, fan, texnologiya, muhandislik va matematika kabi STEM fanlari bo'yicha tayyorlangan mutaxassislarning yetarli darajada ta'minlanmagani jamiyatning innovatsion salohiyatini zaiflashtirishi mumkin. Ma'lumki, STEM fanlari bilan bog'liq gender tafovuti butun dunyoda ko'p yillar davomida saqlanib qolgan. Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston Respublikasida bu masalaga katta e'tibor qaratilayotgani xotin-qizlarning oliy ta'lim va davlat boshqaruvidagi faolligi ortib borayotganidan dalolatdir.

O'qimishli va bilimli ayollarning foydalanilmagan salohiyati nafaqat ayollarning o'zlari, balki butun jamiyat uchun boy berilgan imkoniyatdir. Respublikada bu masalaning ahamiyati tobora ortib borayotganiga qaramay, biz tadqiqotchilarga ushbu hodisani chuqurroq o'rganishga va mas'ul shaxslarga samarali javob choralari ishlab chiqishga to'sqinlik qiladigan ma'lumotlarning yetishmasligiga duch kelyapmiz. Ushbu tadqiqot ishi ishga qabul qilish va ushlab turishda gender nomutanosibligini tushuntirish uchun zarur bo'lgan asosiy omillarni o'rganish va STEM fanlarini rivojlantirishga ko'maklashish orqali O'zbekistondagi ilmiy munozaralarga hissa qo'shishga qaratilgan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu yo'nalishda gender muvozanatiga erishishga qaratilgan tavsiyalar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: STEM fani, ayol olimlar, gender tengligi.

Annotation. The shortage of qualified personnel is one of the key factors limiting innovation, hindering labor productivity growth, and slowing down economic development. In particular, the insufficient availability of well-trained specialists in STEM fields—science, technology, engineering, and mathematics—can weaken a society's innovative potential. It is well known that the gender gap in STEM disciplines has persisted worldwide for many years. Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan places significant emphasis on addressing this issue, as evidenced by the increasing participation of women in higher education and public administration.

The underutilization of skilled and educated women represents a lost opportunity not only for them individually but also for society as a whole. Despite growing recognition of this issue in Uzbekistan, the lack of sufficient data continues to hinder researchers from conducting in-depth studies and developing effective policy responses. This research paper seeks to contribute to academic discussions in Uzbekistan by analyzing the key factors behind gender disparities in recruitment and career retention, as well as fostering the advancement of STEM disciplines. Furthermore, the study presents recommendations aimed at achieving gender balance in this sector.

Keywords: *STEM disciplines, women scientists, gender equality.*

Аннотация. Дефицит квалифицированных кадров является одним из ключевых факторов, сдерживающих инновационную деятельность, мешающих росту производительности труда, экономическому развитию. В частности, недостаточное предложение подготовленных специалистов по STEM дисциплинам, таким как наука, технология, инженерное дело и математика, может ослабить инновационный потенциал общества. Как нам известно, гендерный разрыв связанный с дисциплинами STEM сохраняется на протяжении многих лет во всём мире. В Республике Узбекистан сегодня придаётся большое внимание данному вопросу, о чём свидетельствует повышение участия женщин в высшем образовании и в общественном управлении.

Неиспользованный потенциал подготовленных и дипломированных женщин представляет собой упущенные возможности не только для самих женщин, но и для общества в целом. Несмотря на растущее признание важности этого вопроса в республике, мы сталкиваемся с проблемой нехватки информации, которая препятствует исследователям более углубленно изучать этот феномен и разработать эффективные меры реагирования для ответственных лиц. Данная научная статья призвана содействовать научным дискуссиям в Узбекистане путем рассмотрения основных факторов, необходимых для объяснения гендерного неравенства при подборе и удержании кадров, и содействию развития STEM дисциплин. Кроме того, предложены рекомендации, направленные на достижение гендерного баланса в данном направлении.

Ключевые слова: *STEM наука, женщины учёные, гендерное равенство.*

Introduction.

Gaps in professional training are one of the key factors limiting innovation, hindering labor productivity growth, and slowing economic development. In particular, the shortage of qualified specialists in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) can weaken a society's innovative potential. Empirical studies show that countries with a higher proportion of engineering graduates tend to grow faster than those where other disciplines dominate. We believe that future technological advancements and the adoption of innovations will be directly linked to the characteristics and potential of STEM disciplines.

For many years, a significant gender gap has persisted across all levels of STEM-related fields worldwide. While women have made notable progress in higher education, their participation in these fields remains disproportionately low. This issue is particularly pronounced at the highest levels of academic and professional hierarchies, as well as in the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to data from Uzbekistan, women make up 60% of university graduates and 65% of researchers. However, only 11% of women with higher education in the country are enrolled in STEM disciplines [3, p.15].

At the same time, it is important to highlight that in the past four years, women's participation in senior positions within Uzbekistan's public administration has significantly increased. Gender equality in science, technology, and innovation is not just a matter of fairness. As noted by the European Commission (2008), a more balanced gender distribution contributes to selecting the most talented professionals, regardless of gender. The presence of scientists and engineers from diverse backgrounds, with varying interests and cultural perspectives, leads to better scientific and technological outcomes and ensures the most effective application of these

results [1, p.7]. We believe that achieving gender equality in STEM will not only drive scientific and technological progress but also expand opportunities for women.

The underutilization of highly skilled and educated women represents a major lost opportunity. Many women who show interest in STEM fields either refrain from pursuing an academic degree in these disciplines or change careers due to real or perceived barriers. These obstacles to career advancement deprive society of valuable human resources and undermine national competitiveness and development.

We believe that further research is necessary to identify the root causes of gender disparities in these fields. Based on the findings, effective policy measures should be developed to address the issue.

The main objective of this paper is to contribute to academic discussions on gender equality in STEM within the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Main Part.

In addition, the article examines the main hypotheses and factors proposed in academic literature to explain inequality in hiring, employee retention, and career advancement. The conclusion section provides relevant recommendations based on the research findings.

Although the initial exposure to science and mathematics occurs at the primary education level, higher education plays a decisive role in determining a student's professional path. However, the choice to pursue a career in science and technology largely depends on the experience gained during earlier stages of school education. Therefore, it is essential to focus on teaching STEM subjects in all schools across the country to foster early interest in these fields.

In 2019, Presidential schools were established in Tashkent, Namangan, Khiva, and Nukus. By 2022, these schools had been opened in all regions, offering an advanced curriculum in STEAM subjects based on the Cambridge program. Currently, 14 Presidential schools are operating across the country, providing modern education to students. As we can see, Uzbekistan is paying increasing attention to scientific disciplines at the school level, which will yield positive results in the near future.

Moreover, the smooth transition from secondary to higher education is crucial, as this is the stage where many students may leave the science and technology field. This trend is especially noticeable among women, who are more likely to move away from STEM fields compared to men. Women are generally less inclined than men to choose STEM disciplines when pursuing higher education.

However, the underrepresentation of women in STEM fields is influenced by several factors that negatively affect access to information, recruitment processes, employee retention, and more. In our view, personal preferences, motivation, values, social stereotypes, and cultural norms play a significant role in this issue.

One of the key factors contributing to the lower participation of women in scientific fields is the complexity of career choice. Girls, despite achieving higher grades in mathematics and natural sciences throughout their education, are less likely to choose STEM fields. Compared to boys, they are less inclined to develop a positive attitude toward mathematics or consider it a useful subject for their future. Students' career decisions are shaped by their perceptions of the social roles associated with different professions. Women are more likely to consider future family responsibilities when choosing a career and planning their education path [2, p.35].

A survey conducted among 600 students, in which they were asked about their reasons for choosing a particular specialty, revealed that women tend to prefer careers that do not conflict with family responsibilities and that are beneficial for raising children. These include professions in education, psychology, and medicine.

Therefore, it is believed that women do not consider STEM fields to be family-oriented. Moreover, in some fields (for example, those requiring many laboratory hours), balancing family and work may seem more difficult compared to other fields (such as social sciences). We believe that women are more attracted to fields related to people rather than those involving numbers. Similarly, young men tend to make their choices mainly based on career growth prospects, while women may be motivated by social commitments. In the modern economy, individuals who value social skills and key competencies may find it difficult to pursue engineering research, especially women.

Stereotypes, social norms, and cultural practices also lead to increased discrimination against women in certain research fields. We believe that stereotypes create ideological and social barriers that prevent women from making a significant impact in their professions. Furthermore, stereotypes discourage women from pursuing careers in STEM fields, as these fields are more associated with male characteristics than female ones. We believe that men tend to overestimate their mathematical competencies compared to women, and they are more likely to pursue careers in science, mathematics, and engineering.

In our view, young people base their career choices on the experiences of adult workers. When women succeed in their fields, the next generation is more likely to imitate their success and choose similar paths.

The gender gap in STEM fields, in terms of participation in the labor force, is often wider than the gender gap in educational trajectories. This is because we, as women, encounter significantly greater barriers to career advancement in scientific or engineering fields, despite having the same level of education as men. Indeed, eliminating gender differences in educational achievements will only slightly reduce the gender gap in STEM professions.

The career advancement of women in these fields is characterized by their concentration in lower levels of the hierarchy, while they are not involved in decision-making processes or leadership positions. We believe this is related to the high proportion of women working in male-dominated fields. As a result, women face difficulties when attempting to rise to higher positions due to slow career progression.

After graduation, women must overcome several barriers to enter and advance in their careers.

These processes include subjective hiring procedures: restrictive rules, biased promotion practices, lack of access to networks, stereotypes, labor activity, balance issues, and practices. In the process of nominating a candidate for a leadership position, women may face disciplinary sanctions based on gender, hiring procedures, as well as restrictive provisions and norms. One of the methods for attracting professionals to a specific position is through interviews, evaluations, and recommendation letters, which impact the employment of women. Our research on the hiring process for high-tech organizations shows that gender differences may negatively affect the initially offered salary.

According to IPO data, the number of female inventors has doubled over the past 20 years: from 6.8% in 1998 to 12.7% in 2017, which is the last year for which detailed data is

available. During the same period, the proportion of applications in which at least one female author is listed has increased from 12% to 21%.

By studying the international experience of countries in attracting women to STEM professions, we have concluded that the United States is one of the global leaders. For example, in 2013, President B. Obama’s administration approved a five-year educational strategic plan, the key goal of which was to increase women’s participation in STEM sectors and eliminate the social barriers hindering women’s advancement in STEM professions [3, C.15].

Conclusion.

Analyzing foreign experience shows that applying best practices from abroad, the strategy for achieving gender balance in the STEM sector should not be limited to simply increasing efforts to attract staff. It should also include activities aimed at creating an environment that does not tolerate discrimination against employees and retaining women in technical fields. In our opinion, instead of merely copying foreign practices, it is advisable to consider them and take urgent measures to ensure gender balance in STEM specialization training in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

We recommend implementing the following measures to attract women to the STEM field in Uzbekistan:

- Allocate government grants to support women’s education in developing STEM disciplines;
- Foster collaboration among teachers, businesses, charitable foundations, non-profit organizations, and scientists to conduct scientific and practical research;
- Organize regular seminars to involve girls in STEM professions, featuring renowned female scientists who have achieved high results in science and STEM careers;
- Offer open educational courses in STEM fields for anyone interested;
- One of the effective methods of engaging girls in STEM professions is mentorship, which facilitates interaction between female scientists and female students;
- Attract grants from non-profit organizations to train qualified pedagogical staff for the STEM field.

As we conclude our research, it is important to emphasize that, economically and technologically, the country must actively engage with STEM fields, as well as in the preparation of highly qualified personnel and the inclusion of girls and women in STEM education and employment. The key technologies in this direction include state investments aimed at the development of the STEM sector, grants, competitions, programs, the creation and promotion of new STEM professions, and expanding access to STEM education.

Thus, since Uzbekistan has chosen the path of developing a digital economy, it is necessary not only to overcome the gender gap in STEM fields but also to develop effective measures to eliminate gender discrimination in STEM professions. In our opinion, it is crucial to break the stereotypes associated with the education and subsequent careers chosen by women and inspire them to pursue the exact sciences- both through specialized mentoring programs and by promoting positive examples among female scientists. Using foreign experience as a clear example for the formation and development of women’s human capital, it is essential to unite the efforts of government bodies, the educational and scientific communities, businesses, and civil society organizations to ensure the successful technological future of our republic in the era of the digital economy.

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